

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

At the beginning of my second year as managing editor, I am looking forward to continue working together with the members of our editorial board, the editorial team and the technical support to keep up the success of J.UCS. I'd be very grateful for any suggestions and feedback as to how we could even further improve and develop J.UCS in the future. This year, we'd like to further extend our editorial board, so if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. Furthermore, I'd also like to extend the J.UCS consortium by further partners from the North American and Asia-Pacific region; so please contact me if you and your organization are interested in joining and supporting J.UCS.

In the first issue of this year, we have seven accepted papers from three different regions over the world. Philippe Bon and Simon Collart-Dutilleul from France focus in their work on safety requirement engineering. Edson A. Oliveira Junior et al. introduce in their collaborative research between Brazil and UK a systematic evaluation of software product line architectures. Hyun-Seok Min et al. from Korea put their research aim in the paper on how to derive system behavior from software design. Aleksandar Spasic and Dragan Jankovic from Serbia introduce a model-driven framework for design and production of low-budget stereoscopic TV content. Matias Urbieto et al. introduce in their collaborative research between Argentina and Portugal an aspect-oriented approach for spatial concerns in Web applications. Dana K. Urribarri et al. from Argentina discuss their approach of a hyperbolic level-of-detail tree layout. Finally, Santiago A. Vidal and Claudia Marcos from Argentina focus in their work on aspect refactorings for the spring framework.

Finally, allow me to gratefully thank the members of our editorial board who reviewed not only the published articles but also all the papers that did not make it to publication. Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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